

0.1N DCT or DCB and shake the contents for 30 seconds. After about 5 minutes, add 20 ml of 10% KI solution. Titrate the liberated iodine with 0.1N sodium thiosulphate solution. Run a blank with DCT or DCB solutions alone.

Determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical preparations : The proposed method was employed for the determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical products.

At least 20 tablets of the sample was weighed accurately and pulverized with mortar and pestle. An appropriate amount of the sample was weighed and dissolved in water. The residue was filtered off and diluted to 250 ml so that 10 ml of the solution contained 20 mg of isoniazid. The determination of isoniazid was completed by the recommended procedure by taking 10 ml of the tablet solution.

The results obtained were compared with those obtained by chloramine-T (CAT)⁶, chloramine-B (CAB)⁸, vanadate¹¹, N-bromosuccinimide¹² and British Pharmacopoeia¹³ methods. The results agree favourably with one another.

A study on the interference of some of the excipients which are commonly used in pharmaceutical practice such as mannitol, glucose, lactose, sucrose, starch and sodium chloride was made upto a standing time of 15 minutes. It was found that the excipients examined have no effect on the isoniazid determination under the experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Determination of 4-40 mg of isoniazid was achieved with a maximum error of 0.7% and a standard deviation of 0.1.

Detailed investigation of the system brought out the following points :

(i) The stoichiometry of the oxidation with DCT and DCB can be respectively represented by

$$C_5H_4NCONHNH_2 + CH_3C_6H_4SO_2NCl_2 + H_2O \rightarrow C_5H_4NCOOH + CH_3C_6H_4SO_2NH_2 + 2HCl + N_2$$

and

The presence of benzene sulphonamide among the reaction products was detected by tlc technique. A mixture of petroleum ether, chloroform and *n*-butanol (1 : 1 : 0.5 v/v) was used as the solvent with iodine as the developing reagent ($R_F=0.88$). Paper chromatography was used to identify the *p*-toluene sulphonamide ($R_F=0.905$). Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent, 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl in ethanol as the spray reagent. The presence of isonicotinic acid in the reaction mixture was shown by the colour reaction with sodium pentacyanoammineferroate¹⁴. (ii) Water has no effect on the stoichiometry of oxidation of isoniazid. (iii) The stoichiometry is unaffected by the reversal of order of addition of oxidant and

isoniazid. (iv) Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , K^+ , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-} , ClO_4^- , citric acid and gum acacia (20 mg each) have no influence on the stoichiometry of oxidation of isoniazid.

Interferences : Any species oxidized by excess of DCT or DCB will interfere.

Acknowledgement

One of us (R.S.) gratefully acknowledges financial assistance from the U.G.C., India.

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Studies on the Emulsifying Property of Some Indian Gums at Various Hydrogen Ion Concentrations

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Manuscript received 4 February 1980, revised 27 February 1981, accepted 13 April 1981

IN continuation with the previous work¹⁻³ on the emulsifying property of some Indian gums, the work has been further extended to the study of a few more less common gums which have been described as good medicines for so many diseases⁴⁻⁷. These can be used in small quantities in the form of emulsions. A survey of the literature reveals that almost no work has been done on these gums.

The gums chosen for the present study are as follows :

1. *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall (Bakla, Dhaura, Dhavda) ;
2. *Boswellia serrata* Roxb (Luban, Salai) ;
3. *Acacia nilotica* (Arabic, Babul) ;
4. *Sterculia urens* (Kadai, Gulu) and
5. *Bauhinia retusa* Roxb (Semla, Kandla).

Experimental

The crude gums were dried in vacuo at about 90-100° and then powdered in a pestle and mortar.

NOTES

TABLE 1—DATA FOR 40% KEROSENE OIL EMULSIONS

Emulsion No.	Gums	pH	Initial specific Area $\times 10^3$		Stability coefficient $K \times 10^3$
			Experimentally determined	Graphically determined	
25.	1% Dhavda gum	10.1	5.98 cm^2/gm	4.95 cm^2/gm	10.24
26.	1% Dhavda gum	9.0	5.61	4.89	11.53
27.	1% Dhavda gum	6.0	6.16	5.62	15.87
28.	1% Dhavda gum	3.0	7.61	6.53	16.58
29.	1% Salai gum	11.1	5.16	4.41	5.85
30.	1% Salai gum	9.0	5.27	5.01	17.47
31.	1% Salai gum	6.0	6.81	6.02	16.55
32.	1% Salai gum	3.0	8.89	7.58	14.88
33.	1% Arabic gum	11.9	2.71	—	broken
34.	1% Arabic gum	9.0	4.51	4.26	3.33
35.	1% Arabic gum	6.0	5.48	4.73	10.14
36.	1% Arabic gum	3.0	7.64	6.60	15.56
37.	1% Kadai gum	13.2	—	—	broken
38.	1% Kadai gum	9.0	3.51	3.46	1.96
39.	1% Kadai gum	6.0	5.06	4.78	5.50
40.	1% Kadai gum	3.0	6.57	5.88	16.17
41.	1% Semla gum	9.2	15.54	12.30	15.19
42.	1% Semla gum	9.0	10.26	8.91	13.98
43.	1% Semla gum	6.0	9.01	8.31	8.31
44.	1% Semla gum	3.0	15.28	14.45	3.23

The powdered gums were then purified by the method⁸ described earlier.

One per cent suspension of each gum was made by slightly warming the gum with distilled water at 60-80° over a water bath. Some of them which were not completely soluble in water, were triturated with water. 1% suspension of each gum was adjusted to pH 3, 6 and 9 respectively using glass electrode pH meter. The emulsions were prepared at 30° using the fixed concentration of the gums as 1% keeping the ratio of kerosene oil to water as 40 : 60, by the method as described by Mukherjee and Shukla¹.

The size frequency analyses were done immediately and at different intervals of time on the ageing emulsions by the method of King and Mukherjee⁹. The stability coefficients were computed from the data on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares^{9,10}.

Results and Discussion

The results of globule size distribution analyses are too numerous to quote in full, only a summarised results have been given in Table 1.

Size frequency analysis of kerosene oil emulsions stabilised by various gums at various pH values reveals that finest emulsion is produced with Semla gum at pH 9.2. All gums used produced o/w type of emulsions.

Arabic gum stabilised emulsion was the coarsest of all other five substances.

In Fig. 1 the log values of the specific surfaces are plotted against time as abscissa on graph paper for several emulsions to illustrate the agreement between the data on the change of specific surface with time and the exponential hypothesis as

Fig. 1.

○—Emulsion No. 25 ×—Emulsion No. 30
 ■—Emulsion No. 34 ●—Emulsion No. 35
 △—Emulsion No. 44

earlier¹⁰. The lines were determined by fitting the data to the equation :

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient and K = stability coefficient) by the method of least squares. From the equation K' is measured. The reciprocal of this is a direct measure of stability coefficient (K) and is given in Table 1. It can be seen from the data of Table 1, that Dhavda, Salai, and Semla gums have the stability coefficient values at pH 10.1, 11.1, 9.2 (original pH of the gum suspension) respectively in the following order :

Semla > Dhavda < Salai

In the case of Kadai at pH 13.2, the emulsion was not possible, while in the case of Arabic gum at pH 11.9 the emulsion was possible but it was broken after three days ageing time.

At pH 9, 6, 3 the stability coefficient values of various gums can be arranged in following orders :

Salai > Semla > Dhavda > Arabic > Kadai (at pH 9)

Salai > Dhavda > Arabic > Semla > Kadai (at pH 6)

Dhavda > Kadai > Arabic > Salai > Semla (at pH 3)

Hydrogen ion concentration plays an important role in all the cases, as is evident from the particle size distribution, experimentally as well as graphically determined initial specific areas and the stability coefficient values as is evident from the data of Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratefulness to Prof. T. N. Srivastava, Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, for providing laboratory facilities and to SCST (U. P.) for financial help.

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Entropy Variations of Normal-alkyl Derivatives of Organic Compounds

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Manuscript received 22 July 1980, accepted 1 November 1980

THE homologous series of organic compounds provide a convenient basis for studying the physico-chemical properties of organic compounds. Relationships between the bulk properties of these have recently been established^{1,2,3}. It has been shown that the bulk properties can be expressed as an additive function of the number of carbon atoms, n_c , present in the molecule. Prediction of values of entropy for the normal alkyl derivatives of compounds of homologous series with different functional groups is possible as outlined in this work.

Entropy data as reported by Rossini *et al* on these compounds at 298°K in the gaseous state, are plotted against the number of carbon atoms in the molecule in Fig. 1. It is seen that the entropy of these molecules is a linear function of the number of carbon atoms in the molecule. Minor deviations from linearity are observed with the first two members of a series, in that the entropy is slightly less than expected. For example, in the alkane series the observed entropy for CH₄ is 44.52 cal/mol-deg while the expected value is 45.7 cal/mol-deg from the S° vs n_c curve. This variation in the general trend for the first two members of a series has also been observed earlier^{1,2,3} in the studies of their physico-chemical properties.

The interesting feature of these curves is that the slope in all the cases remains the same being equal to 9.4. It is thus shown that S° is related to n_c of a compound in a series according to equation

$$S^\circ = Nn_c + C \quad \dots (1)$$

where c is a constant characteristic of a compound with a functional group, and N a universal constant of 9.4. Values of C have been estimated from Fig. 1 as 36.5, 40.5, 44.5, 48, 49.5, 50, 50.5, 52, 56.5 and 63.5 for alkanes, nitriles, aldehydes, (fluoro compounds and ethers), alcohols (chloro compounds), amines, sulphides, bromo compounds iodo compounds (thiols and esters), nitro compounds, and nitrates respectively. The substitution of different functional groups in a normal paraffin hydrocarbon produces a significant effect on C , and the compounds with different functional groups can be placed in a series in the order: alkane < nitrile < fluoro = aldehyde ether < alcohol = chloro < amine < sulphide < bromo < iodo = ester < thiol < nitro < nitrate.

It can thus be demonstrated that the entropy of a molecule is additive in nature, depending only on the nature of groups present, each CH₂ group contributing a value of 9.4 cal/mol-deg towards the entropy. Deduction of the entropy value for a